

ANALYSIS OF THE LEGISLATION OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES ON THE PRODUCTION OF CASES OF ADMINISTRATIVE OFFENSES

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Over the past period, a lot of work has been done in our country, worthy of centuries, on the way to building a democratic state based on the rule of law and a free civil society. The issue of ensuring human rights and freedoms as the highest value has risen to the level of state policy.

Special attention was paid to the protection of individual rights. The highest goal of the reforms was determined by such noble aspirations of our people as a peaceful, happy life that has no equal. Principles such as humanism, justice and the rule of law have found their practical expression in the work carried out in the field of reforming the judicial system and liberalizing administrative and criminal legislation.

In the Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis dated January 24, 2020, the head of state paid serious attention to the law enforcement activities of state bodies.

“It is necessary to raise reforms in the field of early warning of offenses to a new level.

We are doing a lot of work to improve the activities of the internal affairs bodies. But they have not yet become a structure that is actually respected by the people.

Their system lacks specific criteria for the protection of public order, the fight against crime, and the provision of public services. In this regard, I think it is important to emphasize once again that it is necessary to continue reforms and turn the internal affairs bodies into real defenders of citizens”¹.

The norms of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan are the main guarantee of ensuring the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens. According to it, the State, its bodies, officials, public associations, citizens act in accordance with the Constitution and laws.

Also, the rights and freedoms of all persons participating in the stage of proceedings on administrative offenses are fully realized.

¹ Послание Президента Республики Узбекистан Шавката Мирзиёева Олий Мажлису (24 января 2020 года) https://nrm.uz/contentf?doc=612860_

The activities of state bodies and officials are regulated by certain laws and subordinate regulatory legal acts. In particular, the activities of the internal affairs bodies to ensure the proceedings in cases of administrative offenses are based on the requirements of a number of laws and subordinate regulatory legal acts. For example, the Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Administrative Responsibility establishes measures to ensure proceedings in cases of administrative offenses. The application of these measures by the internal affairs bodies is a complex process associated with the restriction of human rights.

This implies the need to ensure the rule of law when applying measures to ensure the production of cases of administrative offenses by state bodies.

Proceedings on cases of administrative offenses are a separate type of administrative proceedings and today there is a wide range of bodies (officials) carrying it out. In this regard, an in-depth scientific and theoretical analysis of measures ensuring the proceedings in cases of offenses is of great importance. Within the framework of the subjects applying these measures, a special place is occupied by the administrative and jurisdictional activities of the internal affairs bodies.

Employees of the internal affairs bodies in the process of law enforcement widely apply administrative measures in order to prevent offenses, identify them, eliminate them and ensure that the perpetrator is brought to justice. The correct and rational application of these measures largely depends on the successful resolution of issues such as the protection of public order, the protection of property, the strengthening of legislation, ensuring the rights and legitimate interests of citizens.

In order to ensure the proceedings on cases of administrative offenses by officials of the authorized body on the basis of the Administrative Code and other legislative acts are carried out:

- administrative detention;
- inspection of things and vehicles;
- seizure of things and documents;
- identification of the offender;
- drawing up a protocol, etc.

The proceedings on cases of administrative offenses is a complex process and involves the application of a number of measures in accordance with the provisions provided for by law. Measures to ensure the proceedings in cases of administrative offenses consist of procedural actions related to the restriction of citizens' rights. One of the necessary conditions is the practical application of

measures to ensure record keeping in the legal examination and resolution of cases of administrative offenses. These measures are enshrined in the norms of administrative legislation not only of our republic, but also of foreign states. For example, the Code of Administrative Offences of the Russian Federation establishes measures to ensure record keeping, other than ours.

They are:

- 1) delivery;
- 2) administrative detention;
- 3) personal inspection, inspection of things, inspection of a vehicle located with an individual; inspection of premises belonging to a legal entity, territories, things and documents located there;
- 4) seizure of things and documents;
- 5) suspension from driving a vehicle of the appropriate type;
- 5.1) examination for the state of alcoholic intoxication;
- 6) medical examination for intoxication;
- 7) vehicle detention;
- 8) seizure of goods, vehicles and other things;
- 9) drive;
- 10) temporary prohibition of activity;
- 11) bail for the arrested vessel;
- 12) placement of foreign citizens or stateless persons subject to administrative expulsion from the Russian Federation in the form of forced expulsion from the Russian Federation in special institutions;
- 13) the seizure of property in order to ensure the execution of the decision on the imposition of administrative punishment for the commission of an administrative offense².

The Procedural and Executive Code of the Republic of Belarus on Administrative Offenses lists measures of non-compliance with the administrative process:

- 1) administrative detention of an individual;
- 2) personal search of the detainee;
- 3) seizure of property;
- 4) seizure of things and documents;
- 5) detention and forced towing (evacuation) of a vehicle;
- 6) suspension from driving a vehicle;
- 7) locking the wheels of the vehicle;
- 8) drive;

² <https://legalacts.ru/kodeks/KOAP-RF/razdel-iv/glava-27/statja-27.1/>

9) removal from the premises in which the case of an administrative offense is being considered;

10) temporary restriction of the right of the person in respect of whom the administrative process is being conducted to leave the Republic of Belarus;

11) temporary restriction of the right of a person in respect of whom an administrative process is being conducted to drive motor vehicles, motor small vessels whose engine power exceeds 3.7 kilowatts (5 horsepower), the right to hunt, except in cases when the use of these rights is necessary for a person due to disability or as the only means of obtaining income³.

However, it should be noted separately that the difference between the measures established by the Administrative Code of the Russian Federation and the Republic of Belarus is that they may apply measures to ensure the administrative process in relation to a legal entity (seizure of documents and property belonging to a legal entity; seizure of goods, vehicles and other property belonging to a legal entity).

Taking into account the above and in order to increase the effectiveness of countering offenses by maximizing the use of foreign experience, we believe that this institution has a certain resource for its further improvement.

In conclusion, it should be noted that when state bodies apply measures aimed at ensuring proceedings in cases of administrative offenses, explanations of the rights and obligations of persons regulated by the Code of Administrative Responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan are of particular importance. State bodies are one of the authorized officials responsible for the application of measures aimed at ensuring the proceedings in cases of administrative offenses, as well as ensuring the rule of law in this process. Ensuring the rule of law provides for compliance by state bodies in carrying out activities in this direction with the requirements established by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Code of Administrative Responsibility and regulatory legal acts adopted on their basis.

One of the current issues in the activities of state bodies in the conduct of cases of administrative offenses is a comprehensive study of the received appeals within the requirements of the current regulatory legal acts and ensuring that appropriate measures are taken against persons who have committed offenses.

Использованная литература:

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³ https://kodeksy-by.com/pikoap_rb/8.1.htm

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2. <https://legalacts.ru/kodeks/KOAP-RF/razdel-iv/glava-27/statja-27.1/>
3. https://kodeksy-by.com/pikoap_rb/8.1.htm

